

1 CIRCUIT BREAKER PATTERN

We derive behavioral descriptions of the Circuit Breaker pattern provided by the *Release It!* book. The Circuit Breaker has three states (1) *Closed*, (2) *Open*, and (3) *Half-Open*. The description of the Circuit Breaker behavior is as follow. In case, the state of the Circuit Breaker is *Open*, a calling thread (OS thread) of client does not obtain permission. If the state of the Circuit Breaker is *Closed*, the thread gets the permission to send a request to the protected service. The request's response is either a success or an error (e.g., service is unavailable or busy). Finally, the Circuit Breaker records the result from the service call. IF the the failure percentage is above a threshold then the Circuit Breaker goes to *Open* state. After some times the Circuit Breaker goes into *Half-Open* state. Figure 1 describes the dynamic behavior of the Circuit Breaker pattern via a UML sequence diagram. Figure 1 does not represent the calculation of failure percentage and changing to the *Half-Open* state, which we describe as following.

Figure 1: A dynamic view of the Circuit Breaker in either Closed or Open state

In the *Half-Open* state, the Circuit Breaker allows permission to a configurable number of calls. When the Circuit Breaker records all the results, it computes the failure percentage. If the percentage is greater than or equal to the threshold, the Circuit Breaker switches to the *Open* state. Otherwise, the Circuit Breaker switches to the *Closed* state. The sequence diagram in Figure 2 describes the behavior of the Circuit Breaker in the *Half-Open* state, which allows permission to a configurable number of calls. The outer block represents a loop in which the sequence of asking for permission, execution, and recorded calls are repeated at least for a *minimum number of calls*; then,

the Circuit Breaker decides to trip to open if the percentage of failed calls is greater or equal than the *threshold*.

Figure 2: A dynamic view of Circuit Breaker in Half-Open state

Considering the high-level goals and the behavior of the Circuit Breaker pattern, we derive the following design-level requirements:

Requirement1 The Circuit Breaker must go into the *Open* state when the number of failed calls is above the threshold.

Requirement2 The Circuit Breaker stays in the *Open* state for a fixed duration. Afterward, the system goes into the *Half-Open* state.

Requirement3 No calls get permission when the system is in the *Open* state.

Requirement4 In the *Half-Open* state, the system shall execute only one call¹ to test if the service is back.

Requirement5 The Circuit Breaker goes from the *Half-Open* state to the *Open* state when the number of failed test calls is above the threshold.

Requirement6 The Circuit Breaker goes from the *Half-Open* state to the *Closed* state when the number of failed test calls is below the threshold.

¹In our design specification, we allow the number to be configurable to avoid hard-coding the value.

2 EVENT SOURCING

The *PacificA* design has a concise behavioral description. Therefore, we refer the readers for the details of the behavioral description to the paper written by Lin et al. Here, we provide a high-level overview.

The authors of *PacificA* propose a practical design that offers scalable performance, availability, and guaranteeing strong consistency for replicated log-based storage systems. Generally speaking, strong consistency (aka *linearizability*) means the application only sees a single copy of data, even though the storage is replicated across multiple nodes. Furthermore, the authors claim (informally) that the design is correct.

The important design decision in the protocol is the separation of data replication from configuration management. The data replication part follows the Primary/Backup design, which is responsible for replicating data among existing replicas. In contrast, configuration management is only for holding meta-data regarding the configuration of all replicas and follows an existing consensus algorithm such as Raft. Lin et al. specify a precise requirement in the form of invariant that we name *strongConsistent*: “Let p be the primary and q be any replica in the current configuration, $committed_q \subseteq committed_p \subseteq prepared_q$ ”. The requirement *strongConsistent* must hold after a re-configuration, including (1) change of primary, (2) failure and recovery of a node, and (3) adding a new node. In our design specification, we do not model the addition of a new node, which means enlarging the replica group. However, we model the change of primary and failure/recovery of a node.

3 RETRY

We derived behavioral descriptions of the Retry pattern provided in Microsoft cloud-native patterns collection. The sequence diagram in Figure 3 illustrates the behavior of a request retry. The thread instance delegates the execution of the request to a retry process. The service instance returns either an exception or success. At this point, the retry process enters a loop region, and until the service returns an exception, the retry re-executes the request for a maximum number of *maxAttempt*. Moreover, the retry process applies delay (via *backoff* method) between each re-execution.

We derive the following design-level requirements concerning the high-level goals and behavior of the Retry pattern.

Requirement1 Repeating the request should have a

Figure 3: A dynamic view of Retry behavior

maximum number of attempts.

Requirement2 Repeating of the request should have a back-off strategy, which prevents the client cause crash of already degraded service.